

PHILOSOPHY IN THE STORIES OF KH.DOSTMUHAMMAD

Ergasheva Aziza

Jizzakh state pedagogical university

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Abstract: Literary process of the period of independence literally brought forth unique artistic interpretations of various genres. In this respect, such cases can be observed in the development of storytelling. The narrative genre has its own development in Uzbek literature. Khurshid Dostmuhammad is one of the writers who has significantly contributed to the development of this genre in recent years. In his stories, problems such as suffering in the human heart, conflicts in social life have found their artistic interpretation.

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Literary process of the period of independence literally brought forth unique artistic interpretations of various genres. In this respect, such cases can be observed in the development of storytelling. The narrative genre has its own development in Uzbek literature. Khurshid Dostmuhammad is one of the writers who has significantly contributed to the development of this genre in recent years. In his stories, problems such as suffering in the human heart, conflicts in social life have found their artistic interpretation. In the literature of this period, Nazar Eshanqul, Khurshid Dostmuhammad, Ulug'bek Hamdam, Isajon Sultan, N. Norqabilov, S. Onar, A. We can follow the stories of different characters of a number of creators like Yoldoshev. Here we will focus on the stories that embody such features as symbolism and metaphor.

Literary scholar U. As Normatov noted: "One of the most important features of our literary process in recent years is that our literature is becoming more and more diverse... We also have works of different directions in terms of philosophical basis." From this point of view, we can directly observe this feature in the work of Khurshid Dostmuhammad. It illuminates the unique character of the writer in the story "Jajman". If "market", "market life", "man's daily worries" are described, but "market" is our daily life, and there is symbolism in it, then in "Jajman" we see metaphor: "Hademai, the morning dawns, the world is filled with light ... People wake up, the market wakes up .. the gate of language opens, the commotion begins .. the fog rushes in, flows out ... the seller comes, the buyer comes, the idler comes ... the feet do not stop, the slaves do not stop, the mouths do not stop. .. goes in and out, comes in and goes out ... he says he's getting money, he says he's selling goods ... he puts a bride through the nose of a person with a trick and turns it around in the so-called "market"

tray. We can witness that symbolism, hidden meaning, and deep philosophical concepts are expressed in these thoughts, spoken by the hero of the story, Grandfather Zoroaster. Reading the above interpretations, the reader comes to the understanding that the market means life. Why is a person constantly busy from morning to night, and in the market we meet people of various characters, they are in a hurry to go somewhere, and the seller tries to sell his goods, thinks about his profit, that is how he naturally spends his day. But in these places, human life is the life of the market, just as there are different characters in the market, human life is not even, it sometimes suffers from injustice. As there are not only conflicts in life, but also conflicts in one's own psyche, society also changes through human thinking. In these places, we understand that the philosophical interpretation of the work is skillfully integrated into the subject of the work. The image of a person becoming a slave of lust gives the impression of being depicted through "Jajman". Because he couldn't get enough, he wanted to put the whole market in his small stomach: "I will feed him!" No, I will feed him until his belly bursts!", but every time "I will feed him!" The grown-ups would shout, and Jajman's insatiability remained in his mouth."

N. spoke about the work. Davrboeva writes: "Jajman is seen in this place as bribe-takers, extortionists, in general, as tiny tyrants within the nation." We can call these groups by any name we want." At this point, we feel that we are talking about the person and the image of people who are the cause of the evil of the soul. The image of Grandfather Zardosht, who took place in the subject of the work, stands out. The writer does not directly involve him in the series of events of the work, but through him we can more deeply understand the image of a spiritually mature person, the conflict between good, goodness and evil, and injustice. Since the creation of mankind, the struggle between good and evil has existed forever. But goodness wins slowly, and the truth emerges: "Don't lose your temper, Ahuramazda!... You will enlighten the hearts..." said Grandfather Zardosht, pleading inwardly.

In the story Ahuramaz is the main concept that calls for victory over Ahriman and evil, that is, the world of Jajmans, in bringing forth goodness. That's why grandfather Zoroaster often says "Be aware, be aware, Ahuramazda!... - Ahriman is not dead, Ahuramazda!... You will not be aware, good people, be aware!..."

We can find a lot of works comparing the spiritual world of the East and the West in the works of Kh. Dostmuhammad. In particular, the author's story "The Road to Silence" was very successful in this regard. Adib gives the following explanation about the history of writing this story: "For many years, I have been

influenced by the story "Seven Floors" by the famous Italian writer Dino Bustati. Finally, I freely translated this extraordinary original story and finished the story as a "view" of it. The story is based on the personal views of two polar figures about life and death.

People named Dino Korte, the hero of the story "Seven Floors", and Zahid Yaqin, the hero of "The Road to Quiet House". Both of them end up in the hospital with a minor illness. Both hospital buildings have seven floors. Only in the hospital they place Dino Korte on the seventh floor and Zahid Yaqin on the first floor.

Conclusion

In his interpretation, death is a tragedy for a Westerner. Death is eternal darkness, nothingness. H. Dostmuhammad approaches the problem of life and death based on Eastern philosophy. To a certain extent, it relies on the teachings of Sufism. For example, the name Zahid is also Sufi, the first Sufis were called ascetics. Zahid Yaqin repeats again and again that his soul is getting more refreshed as he approaches death and that a joy is emerging in his heart.

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